

UNIVERSITY OF MESSINA

MIFT DEPARTMENT – MATHEMATICAL AND COMPUTER SCIENCES,

PHYSICAL SCIENCES AND EARTH SCIENCES

Master's Degree Programme in PHYSICS (LM-17)

MOTION MAGNIFICATION AS AN INVESTIGATION TOOL TO STUDY FAILURE MECHANISMS IN POWER DEVICES

Master's Thesis by:

Chiara Tripodi

Supervisor:

Prof. Salvatore Patanè

Co-Supervisor:

Dr. Moreno d'Ambrosio

Academic Year 2024-2025

Summary

	page
List of Abbreviations	I
List of Figures	II
List of Tables	V
Abstract	1
Chapter 1: New Generation Power Devices	2
1.1 Properties and Advantages of WBGs	3
1.2 Limitations	5
1.3 State-of-the-art on Failure Mechanisms	6
Chapter 2: Motion Magnification	8
2.1 Lagrangian Method	10
2.2 Eulerian Methods	13
2.2.1 Pyramid Decomposition	13
2.2.2 Linear Model	17
2.2.3 Phase-Based Model	19
2.3 Deformations Analysis in Power Devices	22
Chapter 3: Materials and Methods	23
3.1 Devices	23
3.2 Test Protocol and Experimental Setup	25
3.2.1 Power Supply and Driving Circuit	25
3.2.2 Electrical Characterization	28
3.2.3 Optical Measurements	29
3.2.4 Controlled Aging Sessions	31
Chapter 4: Data Analysis and Experimental Results	33
4.1 Qualitative Analysis	34
4.2 Quantitative Analysis	37
4.2.1 3D Reconstruction	38
4.3 GaN HEMTs Results	40
4.4 SiC MOSFETs Results	44
Conclusions	46
References	47

List of Abbreviations

BP	Band-Pass
CSP	Complex Steerable Pyramid
DUT	Device Under Test
FIR	Finite Impulse Response
GaN	Gallium Nitride
HEMT	High Electron Mobility Transistor
IIR	Infinite Impulse Response
LP	Laplacian Pyramid
MM	Motion Magnification
MOSFET	Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field Effect Transistor
NI	National Instruments
Si	Silicon
SiC	Silicon Carbide
TTL	Transistor-Transistor Logic
WBGs	Wide Bandgap Semiconductors

List of Figures

	page
Figure 2.1 An example of Motion Magnification: the oscillations of a crane due to the wind are imperceptible in the original sequence but become clearly visible in the magnified video. The two plots on the right show a spatiotemporal representation of the video along the green profile highlighted in the images on the left.	8
Figure 2.2 Schematic representation of the Lagrangian approach: a) first frame containing the object of interest; b) subsequent frame in which the object moved and motion is described by the displacement vector \vec{u} ; c) the same frame after magnification, where the displacement vector is scaled by a user-defined amplification factor α .	10
Figure 2.3 Example of MM using the Lagrangian method: a) original frame; b) magnified frame showing voids caused by object displacement; c) magnified frame after retexturing operations used to fill the gaps.	12
Figure 2.4 Example of Gaussian pyramid with 5 levels.	14
Figure 2.5 Example of Laplacian Pyramid: a filter is applied to the original image f_0 to obtain its blurred version l_0 . Before down sampling, the residual h_0 is computed as the difference between f_0 and l_0 . The residual h_0 contains the most relevant information at that scale and is stored as a level of the pyramid. The process is then repeated for lower scales. Image reproduced from [29].	14
Figure 2.6 Example of a filter for one level of a Steerable Pyramid with four orientations. Reproduced from [29].	15
Figure 2.7 Discrete Fourier Transform is applied to the test image (left panel) and both the amplitude and phase values are recorded, as shown in the plots at the top right. The two plots at the bottom right show the result of an attempted reconstruction using only the amplitudes or only the phases: the amplitude does not contain enough information to reconstruct the image, whereas the phase allows clear identification of edges and main features.	16
Figure 2.8 Example of filters for one level of the CSP with four sub-bands. Reproduced from [32].	16

Figure 2.9 Schematic representation of the linear magnification process: the input video is decomposed using a LP into multiple spatial frequency bands and a temporal filter is applied to each band. The filtered signals are amplified by a factor α , added to the original signal and finally recombined to generate the output video. Temporal filters and magnification factors can be adjusted to suit various applications. Reproduced from [20].	18
Figure 2.10 Schematic representation of phase-based MM process: a) the input images are decomposed through a CSP forming sub-bands of spatial frequencies across multiple scales and orientations; complex filters allow the separation of local amplitude and phase components; b) a temporal filter is applied to the phase components at each scale and orientation; c) the filtered phases are amplified by a factor α and added back to the original signal; d) the output images are reconstructed using the original amplitudes and the amplified phases. Adapted from [21].	20
Figure 3.1 Schematic representation of the packaging and pinout of the devices provided by STMicroelectronics: (a) – (b) SiC MOSFETs; (c) – (d) GaN HEMTs.	23
Figure 3.2 Optical images of the decapsulated devices, with a zoomed-in view of the die: (a) – (b) SiC MOSFET; (c) – (d) GaN HEMT.	24
Figure 3.3 Schematic of the circuit used to carry out the tests.	25
Figure 3.4 a) National Instruments multifunction board installed inside the PC; b) connector block for managing the board’s input/output signals; c) screenshot of the home-made software for signal management.	26
Figure 3.5 a) Amplification driver for the gate-source signal; b) driver’s internal design; c) circuit scheme.	26
Figure 3.6 a) Oscilloscope used to monitor the values of gate voltage and drain-source current; b) current probe that allows to display on the oscilloscope a voltage signal proportional to the drain-source current.	27
Figure 3.7 On the left side: V_{ds} (black line) and I_{ds} (red line) measured at the ends of the transistors during the characterization phase, consisting in a single 10 ms electrical pulse. On the right side: $R_{ds(on)}$ evolution during the pulse, calculated from the data shown in the left side graphs.	29
Figure 3.8 a) Experimental setup for video acquisition; b) illumination system; c) sample holder with adjustable tilt.	30
Figure 3.9 a) Liquid-cooling system; b) configuration of a GaN HEMT mounted on the cooling system during the aging session.	32

Figure 3.10 V_{ds} and I_{ds} across the transistors during a switching event of the controlled aging phase. 32

Figure 4.1 Frames extracted from the original and magnified videos of a GaN HEMT (top) and a SiC MOSFET (bottom) together with a colour map to emphasize the differences. The selected frames represent the initial condition, before the current pulse, and the moment of maximum deformation. The colour maps highlight intensity variations with opposite signs. 35

Figure 4.2 Frames extracted from the original and processed videos of a GaN HEMT. The first row shows three frames from the original video captured before the current pulse, during the excitation, and after the complete dissipation of the generated heat; the second row reports the corresponding frames after applying the magnification algorithm; the third row displays the difference maps between each original frame and its magnified counterpart. 36

Figure 4.3 Schematic of the acquisition system geometry, highlighting the DUT reference frame (orange dashed line) and the camera reference frame (solid blue line). 38

Figure 4.4 Out-of-plane (z) deformation versus time for a GaN HEMT at several points selected on the DUT surface. The inset shows an optical image of the DUT with the measurement points highlighted; the colour of each point corresponds to the colour used to represent its deformation curve. 40

Figure 4.5 Comparative analysis after the aging sessions. Plots represent the DUT deformations after a total stress time of 16 hours (light blue), 19 hours (blue), 20 hours (green) and 32 hours (yellow); vibrometer data are everywhere reported in red. On the right side of each plot: top, a picture of DUT surface with the point of vibrometric measurement marked in red; bottom, the first frame of MM video at the corresponding age, with the point of analysis marked in the same colour of the solid line in the plot. 42

Figure 4.6 Deformation over time for SiC devices. Each plot shows the attempted reconstruction of the out-of-plane motion for the point marked in the images above. The contribution of external vibrations is comparable to the magnitude of the phenomenon under investigation, making quantitative analysis unreliable. 44

List of Tables

	page
Table 1.1 Comparison of the main properties of Si, 4H-SiC and GaN.	3
Table 3.1 Specifications of the investigated devices.	24
Table 3.2 Specifics of the two experimental setups.	27
Table 4.1 Parameters for video processing.	34
Table 4.2 Comparison of the maximum deformation amplitude measured with the two techniques.	43

Abstract

The field of electronics has been revolutionized by the adoption of wide bandgap (WBG) semiconductors, such as silicon carbide (SiC) and gallium nitride (GaN), for the development of next-generation power devices. These materials are highly desirable due to their excellent electrical and thermal properties. However, their widespread adoption is still limited by issues related to the long-term reliability of the devices and by the incomplete understanding of the physical mechanisms leading to device failure. Among the various failure mechanisms, thermomechanical deformations induced by current flow emerge as one of the main threats to the structural integrity of these devices. Nevertheless, the impact of these mechanisms on device performance remains relatively underexplored.

This thesis aims to introduce a novel investigation method capable of providing direct measurements of the deformations experienced by a device during its operation, thereby enabling the study of their dynamics. Specifically, I actively worked on the development of both the analysis protocol and the complete experimental setup required to visualize the device surface under real operating conditions. The resulting images are then processed using Motion Magnification algorithms, a computational technique that allows the amplification and visualization of otherwise imperceptible motions. This well-established image-processing technique is here applied for the first time to studies in the field of electronics.

The first chapter explores the properties of WBG materials and reviews the current state of the art regarding reliability issues affecting these devices. The second chapter focuses on the Motion Magnification algorithms currently in use, providing a detailed discussion of the theoretical principles underlying each developed model and guiding the selection of the most suitable method for the case under study. The third chapter is devoted to the measurement protocol. The experimental setup was entirely designed and developed at the Nanotechnology Laboratory of the University of Messina, while the analysed devices (SiC MOSFETs and GaN HEMTs) were provided by STMicroelectronics. Finally, the fourth chapter presents and discusses the obtained results.

Chapter 1

New Generation Power Devices

In recent years, Power Electronics has taken on a strategic role in the ecological transition, contributing to the development of more sustainable energy systems with reduced environmental impact. From the automotive sector to renewable energy and telecommunications, the ability to efficiently convert and manage electrical energy is a key factor in reducing both energy consumption and emissions.

This research field has experienced steady growth, initially driven by semiconductor devices based on silicon (Si), the undisputed reference material for design and large-scale production. However, the intrinsic limitations of Si are becoming increasingly restrictive for modern high-performance applications, which require smaller and lighter components that can operate at high voltages and temperatures [1].

To meet these demands, attention has progressively shifted toward new materials with superior performance compared to Si, namely wide bandgap (WBG) semiconductors. Among the various materials classified as WBGs, the two identified as the most promising for the next generation of power devices are silicon carbide (SiC) and gallium nitride (GaN). Thanks to their superior physical properties, these materials enable the design of thinner devices capable of operating at voltages, frequencies and temperature that are prohibitive for conventional silicon-based technology [2] [3].

Understanding both the advantages and the limitations of these materials is therefore essential for the development of the next generation of power devices.

1.1 Properties and Advantages of WBGs

Wide bandgap (WBG) semiconductors are fundamentally defined by their bandgap energy values, which are significantly larger than those of conventional semiconductors. The bandgap energy E_g is the minimum energy required to excite an electron from the valence band to the conduction band. At room temperature, silicon has $E_g \approx 1.12 \text{ eV}$, whereas for SiC and GaN the values are approximately three times higher [3].

Table 1.1 summarizes some of the main properties of GaN and SiC (4H polytype) compared to silicon.

PROPERTIES (T=300K)	Si	4H-SiC	GaN
Bandgap	Indirect	Indirect	Direct
Bandgap Energy (eV)	1.12	3.26	3.45
Critical Electric Field (MV/cm)	0.3	2.5 – 3	3 – 3.5
Electron Mobility (cm²/V·s)	1400	900	2000
Saturation Velocity (×10⁷ cm/s)	1	2	2.5
Thermal Conductivity (W/cm·K)	1.5	4.9	1.3

Table 1.1 Comparison of the main properties of Si, 4H-SiC and GaN.

A larger bandgap implies that more energy is required to generate electron-hole pairs. A direct consequence is the suppression of thermal generation of intrinsic carriers, resulting in reduced leakage currents and improved stability at high temperatures. The intrinsic carrier concentration n_i represents the number of thermally generated electron-hole pairs in an intrinsic semiconductor and follows the relation:

$$n_i \propto T^{\frac{3}{2}} \times \exp\left(-\frac{E_g}{2k_b T}\right).$$

This expression shows how the bandgap energy exponentially controls the thermal generation of intrinsic charge carriers: even modest increases in E_g lead to significant reductions in n_i . At 300 K, silicon has $n_i > 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, whereas for SiC $n_i \approx 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, a

difference of 17 orders of magnitude. This explains why SiC can operate at high temperatures where silicon would be overwhelmed by thermally generated carriers, losing its semiconducting behaviour [4].

Another key parameter is the critical electric field E_c , defined as the maximum electric field that a material can withstand before undergoing dielectric breakdowns, resulting in an uncontrolled increase in current (avalanche breakdown). Materials with larger bandgaps exhibit higher critical fields, approximately proportional to $E_g^{2.5}$ [5]. Indeed, for SiC and GaN the values of E_c are about ten times higher than that of silicon. This improvement arises because wider bandgaps require higher energies to trigger avalanche multiplication, a process in which high-energy charge carriers generate additional carriers through collisions with the lattice. Such energies can only be reached at higher electric fields. For a given material thickness, a higher E_c therefore allows the device to sustain higher voltages, a property that is exploited in device design to achieve thinner structures [6].

Both SiC and GaN offers superior performance compared to Si, but they exhibit distinct characteristics that make them suitable for different applications [7] [8]. SiC is characterized by its high thermal conductivity, which is essential for heat management and for keeping the junction temperature within operational limits, making it ideal for high-voltage applications (600 – 1200 V). On the other hand, GaN excels in high-frequency applications due to its high electron mobility and saturation velocity, enabling switching at high frequencies (MHz order) with reduces switching losses.

1.2 Limitations

As highlighted in the most recent literature, WBGs are now actively competing with silicon in the market [9], however their full adoption still faces significant challenges [8] [10]. The main open issues include:

- Control of crystalline defects
- Optimization of fabrication processes
- Thermal management
- Reliability-related concerns.

Moreover, the growth of SiC and GaN crystals is a slow and complex process that requires equipment completely different from that used for Si, making the establishment of new production lines extremely costly.

The most critical concern in the development of WBG devices is long-term reliability, a fundamental requirement in power electronics. These devices must exhibit extremely high reliability and robustness, as they often play a *mission critical role*, where their failure can compromise the operation of the entire system [11]. However, WBG-based technologies are relatively young, therefore manufacturing processes have not yet reached full maturity and, most importantly, the physical mechanisms responsible for device failure are not yet fully understood.

In principle, reliability tests are designed to assess whether a device can withstand all the stresses it may encounter in real applications [12], but in practice current testing protocols are often inherited from Si technologies and do not account for the specific characteristics of WBG materials, which operate at much higher power densities. This different operating regime can lead to the emergence of degradation mechanisms that are not entirely comparable to those typically observed in silicon devices. Therefore, the study of failure mechanisms in WBG devices remains an active research field.

1.3 State-of-the-art on Failure Mechanisms

In general, power devices are subject to a wide range of degradation factors: some originate from the device design or packaging structure, others are related to the quality of manufacturing processes, while others arise from the extreme operating conditions typical of high-power applications, which include significant thermal, electrical and mechanical stress [11]. These three sources of stress do not act independently but give rise to coupled thermo-mechanical phenomena, whose understanding is essential.

One of the most critical aspects of WBG devices is the high power dissipated during operation [13]: when current flows through the device, the heat generated by the Joule effect is proportional to the on-state resistance $R_{ds(on)}$, according to the well-known relation

$$P = I^2 \times R.$$

Even with initially low resistance values, high operating currents can generate significant localized heating, which in turn induces deformations affecting the entire device. However, the device consists of multiple material layers (substrate, semiconductor, metallization, etc.) each characterized by a different coefficient of thermal expansion. This mismatch generates internal stresses and interfacial instabilities between the layers, progressively compromising the structural integrity of the transistor. Repeated stress also promotes the formation and propagation of defects, which alter the electrical parameters of the device, including channel resistance. An increase in $R_{ds(on)}$ leads to higher power dissipation, further amplifying the stress effects. This feedback loop of mutually reinforcing mechanisms accelerates the degradation until failure occurs.

In this framework, the distinction between electrical, thermal and mechanical degradation loses its significance, giving way to a more integrated view of the phenomenon. Nevertheless, the existing literature provides an extensive description of individual degradation mechanisms in SiC and GaN devices, with particular focus on electrical instabilities and thermal aspects [11] [14], while studies on thermos-mechanical deformation effects remain limited [15].

In particular, the observation and quantification of deformations as a potential early indicator of degradation remain largely unexplored. This is mainly due to the lack of efficient, non-invasive methodologies that can be easily integrated into experimental (and industrial) protocols to observe such deformations. The extremely small scale of these phenomena (micrometric and sub-micrometric) makes them difficult to visualize, as they fall below the sensitivity of conventional optical systems. Although well-established

interferometric techniques allow high-resolution measurements, no study to date has developed a system capable of directly visualizing the deformations occurring in a device during its operation.

This thesis aims to introduce a new opto-computational methodology based on *Motion Magnification*, capable of providing fast and contactless measurements with a relatively low-cost setup. Motion Magnification is a well-established technique that has been widely used to study vibrations in macroscopic structures, such as cranes and bridges. The next chapter is devoted to this technique, providing a detailed discussion of the theoretical principles underlying the different developed models.

Chapter 2

Motion Magnification

Motion Magnification (MM) is a set of computational techniques that make visible to the human eye movements otherwise imperceptible, through careful processing of video images. This research field has been developed over the past 20 years primarily by the MIT Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory (CSAIL) and has found applications in a wide range of domains, from structural engineering to medical diagnostics [16][17][18].

Figure 2.1 An example of Motion Magnification: the oscillations of a crane due to the wind are imperceptible in the original sequence but become clearly visible in the magnified video. The two plots on the right show a spatiotemporal representation of the video along the green profile highlighted in the images on the left.

MM techniques can be broadly classified into two main categories: Lagrangian methods and Eulerian methods, named after the corresponding frameworks in fluid dynamics which differ in their approach to motion representation.

The first implemented technique was based on the Lagrangian approach [19] and was proposed by Liu et al. in 2005. In 2012, the work of Wu et al. introduced the linear Eulerian method [20], achieving significant improvements in both computational efficiency and result quality. Subsequently, in 2013 Wadhwa et al proposed the phase-based Eulerian method [21] which uses complex spatial filters to extract motion information from images. This method proved to be faster and more accurate than the previous ones and further improvements to the convolutional filters have since been proposed [22], culminating in

the implementation of a machine learning-based approach in 2018 [23] where filters are replaced by a neural network. In the following sections, the theoretical foundations of each of these methods are presented.

2.1 Lagrangian Method

In fluid mechanics, the Lagrangian framework describes a fluid by subdividing it into particles that are individually tracked by the observer, following the displacement of each particle over time to reconstruct its trajectory. Similarly, Lagrangian MM tracks the displacement over time of selected points of interest within an image and subsequently amplifies it.

Figure 2.2 Schematic representation of the Lagrangian approach: a) first frame containing the object of interest; b) subsequent frame in which the object moved and motion is described by the displacement vector \vec{u} ; c) the same frame after magnification, where the displacement vector is scaled by a user-defined amplification factor α .

The process is divided into multiple stages aimed at optimizing the final result; it includes corrective steps and clustering procedures to remove undesired global motion and to group together portions of the image that move coherently. Motion is estimated locally by selecting points of interest and using optical flow techniques to track their trajectories between consecutive frames.

The underlying idea is that, given a sequence of images, it is possible to compute a vector that maps each pixel to its corresponding in the next frame, assuming that, although the object moves over time, its brightness remains constant [24].

Let's suppose to work on two consecutive frames and to denote the image intensity as $I(x, y, t)$, where (x, y) are the pixel coordinates and t is time. Hence, the presence of a flow vector $\vec{u} = (u_x, u_y)$ implies:

$$I(x, y, t) = I(x + u_x, y + u_y, t + 1). \quad (1)$$

The Optical Flow equation is derived by performing Taylor expansion of the right-hand side of (1), obtaining:

$$I(x, y, t) = I(x, y, t) + \frac{\partial I}{\partial x} u_x + \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} u_y + \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} + \mathcal{O}(u^2)$$

which simplifies to:

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial x} u_x + \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} u_y + \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} = 0. \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) imposes a constraint on the intensity variation along the direction of motion but cannot be uniquely solved for each pixel as it contains two unknowns, u_x and u_y . The two main approaches used to introduce an additional constraint are local minimization [25] or global minimization [26], two methods both based on minimizing an error function.

The first one, known as Lucas-Kanade approach, computes the flow vector using a least-squares method. A window centred on the pixel of interest (typically 7×7 or 9×9) is selected, within the motion is assumed to be uniform. By minimizing the sum of squared errors, the following linear system is obtained:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sum_k \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial x}\right)^2 & \sum_k \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial x}\right) \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial y}\right) \\ \sum_k \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial x}\right) \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial y}\right) & \sum_k \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial y}\right)^2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \sum_k \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial x}\right) \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial t}\right) \\ \sum_k \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial y}\right) \left(\frac{\partial I_k}{\partial t}\right) \end{pmatrix}$$

where k indexes each pixel within the selected window.

In the second method, introduced by Horn and Schunck, a global regularization is imposed on the entire optical flow field, rather than on individual vectors. A functional E is defined as:

$$E = \iint \left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial x} u_x + \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} u_y + \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \mu^2 \left(|\nabla u_x|^2 + |\nabla u_y|^2 \right) dx dy$$

where the integrand terms are, respectively, the brightness constancy constraint introduced in (2) and the smoothness of the optical flow field, controlled by a real parameter μ that determines the strength of the regularization. The goal is to minimize this functional by iteratively solving the associated Euler-Lagrange equations.

Once the displacement vectors are obtained, the image is segmented into layers and each pixel is assigned to a layer based on motion, colour and spatial connectivity. The user can now specify which layers to magnify and by what factor. Motion amplification is achieved by scaling the displacement vector $\vec{u} = (u_x, u_y)$ by the selected magnification factor α .

Although effective, this method is computationally expensive and may introduce artifacts. In particular, when a point of interest is displaced, it leaves behind a void that must be filled using complex retexturing techniques.

Figure 2.3 Example of MM using the Lagrangian method: a) original frame; b) magnified frame showing voids caused by object displacement; c) magnified frame after retexturing operations used to fill the gaps.

2.2 Eulerian Methods

Eulerian methods can in turn be divided into two categories: linear and phase-based approach. They differ for the adopted mathematical model and the type of spatial decomposition, but they both share the goal of amplifying motion in a video without explicitly computing it via optical flow, which is the main limitation of the Lagrangian approach.

The inspiration comes from Eulerian perspective used in fluid dynamics: instead of tracking individual particles and following their motion, one observes the temporal variation on system properties (such as velocity or pressure) at fixed points in space. Similarly, Eulerian MM analyses the intensity values of pixels and tracks their variations across video frames.

Before going into details of the processes underlying the two proposed methods, it is useful to introduce the concept of *Pyramid Decomposition*, a widely used technique in image processing that is employed in both approaches.

2.2.1 Pyramid Decomposition

Is a multiscale decomposition of an image: through the successive application of convolutional filters, the process generates a sequence of images with progressively reduced size and resolution, resulting in a hierarchical structure from which the term “pyramidal” originates [27]. The advantage of this decomposition lies in its ability to reveal information that may not be visible at a given scale but can be detected at another.

Several types of pyramids are known, each with specific properties and advantages: a common example is the Gaussian one, in which the image is repeatedly blurred and down sampled by a factor 2 in each direction, meaning that the number of pixels is halved in each spatial dimension at every filtering step.

An example is given in the following Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4 Example of Gaussian pyramid with 5 levels.

In the context of MM, the linear Eulerian method relies on the Laplacian Pyramid (LP), while the phase-based method uses the Complex Steerable Pyramid (CSP) [28]. Both of them extract information about the spatial frequencies present in the image and form an overcomplete system, meaning that they contain more than enough information for reconstructing the image.

LP is very similar to the Gaussian one, but it stores at each level the difference between the original image and its blurred version, resulting in a hierarchy of spatial frequency bands.

Figure 2.5 Example of Laplacian Pyramid: a filter is applied to the original image f_0 to obtain its blurred version l_0 . Before down sampling, the residual h_0 is computed as the difference between f_0 and l_0 . The residual h_0 contains the most relevant information at that scale and is stored as a level of the pyramid. The process is then repeated for lower scales. Image reproduced from [29].

LP behaves as a band-pass filter: referring to Figure 2.5, each level of the pyramid i contains the residuals h_i that capture the most relevant details at that scale [30]. Only the last level consists directly of the lowest resolution image, rather than the corresponding residual, in order to enable reconstruction of the original image.

Steerable Pyramids further incorporate orientation into the decomposition: at each level multiple versions of the same filter, each rotated by a given angle, are applied to the image, producing several sub-bands corresponding to different orientations [31]. Figure 2.6 shows an example of a filter for one level with four orientations spaced by 45° .

Figure 2.6 Example of a filter for one level of a Steerable Pyramid with four orientations. Reproduced from [29].

Since the pyramid captures information about spatial frequencies across different orientations, the decomposition is typically performed in the frequency domain, i.e. the filters are applied after computing the Discrete Fourier Transform of the image. The highest level of the pyramid contains the highest frequency components (fine details) and, while moving down the pyramid, frequencies are progressively reduced to the final low-pass residual component. In the complete pyramid, each level is composed of multiple sub-bands each storing the amplitudes associated with different orientations.

CSP is a particular case of Steerable Pyramid in which complex-valued filters are used as convolutional kernels, allowing the extraction of both amplitude and local phase associated with the spatial frequencies present in the image. Typically, the amplitude is visualized, as it describes how information is distributed across frequencies; however, it is actually the phase that carries the most critical information. In fact, it is not possible to reconstruct an image using only amplitudes, whereas a good approximation can be obtained using only the phases, as shown in Figure 2.7 [32].

Figure 2.7 Discrete Fourier Transform is applied to the test image (left panel) and both the amplitude and phase values are recorded, as shown in the plots at the top right. The two plots at the bottom right show the result of an attempted reconstruction using only the amplitudes or only the phases: the amplitude does not contain enough information to reconstruct the image, whereas the phase allows clear identification of edges and main features.

This property is related to the concept of *Phase Congruency*, according to which the main structural features of an image, such as edges or corners, emerge at points where all the Fourier components are in phase with each other [33].

Another advantage of CSP arises from the symmetry of the frequency domain: components corresponding to two opposite directions, θ and $\theta + \pi$, are complex conjugates and therefore contain redundant information. One can therefore consider only orientations within the interval $[0, \pi]$, reducing the number of filters required for the decomposition and the number of coefficients to store. This results in improved computational efficiency without loss of information.

Figure 2.8 Example of filters for one level of the CSP with four sub-bands. Reproduced from [32].

2.2.2 Linear Model

The first Eulerian method was proposed by Wu et al. in 2012 [20] and it analyses temporal variations in pixel intensity. The mathematical theory is still based on a Taylor expansion, as in the Lagrangian case, but now we avoid explicit motion estimation by operating directly on intensity values. The technique involves spatial decomposition of the video using a LP, producing multiple representations of the video composed of the residuals at different spatial scales. Each level of the pyramid is processed independently by tracking the temporal variations of pixel intensities, described by the function $I(x, y, t)$. A temporal band-pass filter is applied to isolate the frequencies of interest. The filtered signal is then multiplied by a user-defined magnification factor α and the resulting signal is added back to the original one during pyramid reconstruction. At the end, we obtained an output video in which motion is amplified while preserving the spatiotemporal coherence of the image.

To further clarify the process, let's consider a spatially mono-dimensional signal $I(x, t)$ representing the intensity at position x and time t . The analysis can be easily extended to the real two-dimensional case. The observed intensity can be expressed as function of a temporal displacement $\delta(t)$ from the original position, i.e. if for the first frame we have

$$I(x, 0) = f(x),$$

then for subsequent frames:

$$I(x, t) = f(x + \delta(t)).$$

The goal of MM is to synthesize a new signal

$$\hat{I}(x, t) = f(x + (1 + \alpha)\delta(t))$$

in which the displacement $\delta(t)$ is amplified by a factor $(1 + \alpha)$.

Assuming a small $\delta(t)$ we can expand $f(x + \delta(t))$ using Taylor series

$$I(x, t) = f(x) + \delta(t) \frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} + \mathcal{O}(u^2).$$

The intensity difference between each frame and a reference frame (typically the first one) is given by

$$B(x, t) = I(x, t) - I(x, 0) = \delta(t) \frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x}$$

which is exactly the portion of signal to amplify and add back to $I(x, t)$.

From a computational perspective, the signal $B(x, t)$ corresponds to the output of a band-pass filter that removes the DC component $f(x)$.

The processed signal is therefore:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{I}(x, t) &= I(x, t) + \alpha B(x, t) = f(x) + \delta(t) \frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} + \alpha \delta(t) \frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} = \\ &= f(x) + (1 + \alpha) \delta(t) \frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} = f(x + (1 + \alpha) \delta(t)).\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

where the last equality in (3) is given from the reconstruction of Taylor expansion. This highlights the key difference with Lagrangian method: the amplified signal $\tilde{I}(x, t)$ is obtained without explicit calculation of the displacement $\delta(t)$.

This computation is performed for each frame and at each level of the pyramid: the first frame remains unchanged while all subsequent frames are iteratively updated according to equation (3) until the full video is reconstructed.

Figure 2.9 Schematic representation of the linear magnification process: the input video is decomposed using a LP into multiple spatial frequency bands and a temporal filter is applied to each band. The filtered signals are amplified by a factor α , added to the original signal and finally recombined to generate the output video. Temporal filters and magnification factors can be adjusted to suit various applications. Reproduced from [20].

Movements present in the video are effectively amplified, however the method still exhibits intrinsic limitations due to its theoretical assumptions: since it relies on a first-order Taylor expansion, the model is valid only for small displacements values, where higher order terms are really neglectable. For larger motions, the final video may exhibit artifacts wherever $\frac{\partial^2 f(x)}{\partial x^2}$ is large.

Another drawback is the sensitivity to noise: since the amplification is applied directly on image intensity, any noise present in the original signal is linearly amplified along with the

motion. This severely limits the usable values of α and makes the method unsuitable to process videos with a low signal-to-noise ratio.

2.2.3 Phase-Based Model

In 2013 Wadhwa et al. [21] proposed an innovative approach based on the analysis of local phase instead of amplitude. The goal was to overcome the intrinsic limitations of previous methods, therefore the new model must:

- a) be able to manipulate movements in a video without explicit calculating displacements, which is the strong limitation of Lagrangian model;
- b) adopt a mathematical model not based on a Taylor series expansion, thus removing all limitations on amplification factor values and noise management.

The proposed method is inspired by the studies on phase-based optical flow [34] [35]. The main idea is that a spatial translation can be represented as a phase variation in Fourier domain. A first, intuitive explanation can be given by considering once again the one-dimensional signal $I(x, t)$ such that

$$I(x, t) = \begin{cases} f(x), & t = 0 \\ f(x + \delta(t)), & t > 0. \end{cases}$$

By adopting the Fourier series decomposition, we can express the signal as a sum of sinusoids:

$$f(x) \stackrel{FT}{\Rightarrow} \sum_{\omega} A_{\omega} e^{i\omega x}$$

$$f(x + \delta(t)) \stackrel{FT}{\Rightarrow} \sum_{\omega} A_{\omega} e^{i\omega(x+\delta(t))}$$

and here we can clearly see the relationship between spatial translation $\delta(t)$ and phase variation in the frequency domain

$$\varphi = \omega x \rightarrow \varphi = \omega(x + \delta(t)).$$

By selecting a single frequency ω , we obtain the associated sinusoid

$$S_{\omega}(x, t) = A_{\omega} e^{i\omega(x+\delta(t))}$$

whose phase can be manipulated to amplify motion. However, we first need to isolate the phase information related to motion and, to this end, a band-pass filter is applied to select relevant components.

The result of this filtering operation is precisely the component

$$B_\omega(x, t) = \omega\delta(t)$$

which can be scaled by a factor α and reintroduced into $S_\omega(x, t)$, yielding a new sinusoid $\hat{S}_\omega(x, t)$ whose phase is increased by a factor $(1 + \alpha)$

$$\hat{S}_\omega(x, t) = S_\omega(x, t)e^{i\alpha B_\omega} = A_\omega e^{i\omega(x+(1+\alpha)\delta(t))}. \quad (4)$$

Applying the inverse transform to (4), we recover the signal in the spatial domain

$$\hat{S}_\omega(x, t) \xrightarrow{(FT)^{-1}} f(x + (1 + \alpha)\delta(t))$$

in which the motion is amplified by the same factor $(1 + \alpha)$.

However, in the case of real two-dimensional images, the process must account for the spatial distribution of frequencies in two dimensions and analyse both amplitude and phase components. Therefore, a spatial decomposition based on the CSP is employed, as illustrated in Figure 2.10 (a).

Figure 2.10 Schematic representation of phase-based MM process: a) the input images are decomposed through a CSP forming sub-bands of spatial frequencies across multiple scales and orientations; complex filters allow the separation of local amplitude and phase components; b) a temporal filter is applied to the phase components at each scale and orientation; c) the filtered phases are amplified by a factor α and added back to the original signal; d) the output images are reconstructed using the original amplitudes and the amplified phases. Adapted from [21].

The pyramid is constructed using a complex filter as its basis, whose real and imaginary parts are functions that differs in parity. This pair is iteratively rotated and scaled to generate the appropriate filter the various scales and orientations of the pyramid. These filters are applied to the Fourier transform of the original image and return a set of complex values $C_{\omega,\theta}$, known as pyramid coefficients, where ω and θ denote the scale (level) and orientation (sub-band), respectively.

Each coefficient contains all of the required information to reconstruct amplitude and local phase associated with each pixel. Denoting by $A(x, y)$ the amplitude and by $\varphi(x, y)$ the phase for the pixel of coordinates (x, y) , the following relations hold:

$$\begin{cases} A(x, y) = |C_{\omega,\theta}| = \sqrt{(Re(C_{\omega,\theta}))^2 + (Im(C_{\omega,\theta}))^2} \\ \varphi(x, y) = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{Im(C_{\omega,\theta})}{Re(C_{\omega,\theta})}\right). \end{cases}$$

This operation is repeated for all scales and orientations, associating amplitude and phase maps with each frame.

The mathematical model presented for the one-dimensional case remains conceptually valid: phase variations over time correspond to small local displacements that can be amplified [36]. Only the phase variations that survive temporal filtering correspond to the motion of interest and are therefore multiplied by the amplification factor α chosen by the user. Images are reconstructed by applying the inverse CSP transform, using the original amplitudes and the modified phases.

The phase-based method has proven to be highly effective for amplifying small motions and represents a significant improvement over previous approaches. Processing only the local phase allows for better noise handling and enables the use of higher amplification factors. The quality of the results is significantly improved: spatial details are preserved more faithfully, motion representation remains coherent, and visual artifacts are greatly reduced.

The underlying theory has proven to be robust and has remained largely unchanged over time; the only improvements introduced in the literature concern the design of filter banks used for the pyramid decomposition [22].

2.3 Deformation Analysis in Power Devices

MM techniques have gained significant attention over the years due to their ability to extract dynamic information from simple video sequences. This approach already represents a substantial shift from conventional methodologies, which often require sensors in physical contact with the object or invasive measurement systems. For this reason, the various MM models developed over time have been adopted across numerous scientific fields; however, to date, none of them has been applied to the study of the deformations experienced by an electronic device when current flows through it, which is precisely the context of this thesis.

For the purposes of this work, videos of the transistors during operation were initially acquired. Considering the characteristics of the recorded images and the constraints imposed by the experimental setup, a phase-based approach was selected to enhance the thermomechanical deformations of the device. In particular, Lagrangian and linear methods were excluded due to their lower reliability when processing grayscale, low-resolution images; the phase-based method, on the other hand, is well suited for analysing small images and offers improved robustness to noise.

The videos were further processed to quantify the magnitude of the deformations, using a computational technique that exploits the relationship between local phase variations and motion [37] [38], combined with a three-dimensional motion reconstruction model, which is necessary to correctly interpret the observed displacements. This integrated approach makes it possible to obtain a detailed description of the deformation dynamics occurring in a device during its operation.

In the following chapter, a detailed description of the experimental setup used for the acquisitions will be provided. Furthermore, in order to validate the technique, the results were compared with those obtained using a laser vibrometer.

Chapter 3

Materials e Methods

3.1 Devices

The analyses were carried out on commercially available devices provided by STMicroelectronics, namely four SiC MOSFETs (Metal–Oxide–Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistors) and five GaN HEMTs (High Electron Mobility Transistors).

Figure 3.1 Schematic representation of the packaging and pinout of the devices provided by STMicroelectronics: (a) – (b) SiC MOSFETs; (c) – (d) GaN HEMTs.

The devices are generally packaged as shown in Figure 3.1(a, c). However, the performed analyses require the chip surface (die) to be exposed, therefore the company also carried out the decapsulation process, providing all devices already open and with the die exposed, as shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Optical images of the decapsulated devices, with a zoomed-in view of the die: (a) – (b) SiC MOSFET; (c) – (d) GaN HEMT.

Table 3.1 summarized the specifications of the two types of transistors investigated, as extracted from the datasheet provided by the company together with the devices.

DUT	GAN HEMT	SIC MOSFET
Breakdown voltage ($V_{ds \text{ max}}$)	650 V	1200 V
Max $I_{ds \text{ DC}}$	25 A	129 A
Typical Static $R_{ds(on)}$	49 m Ω	15 m Ω
Total Power Dissipated (at 25°C)	305 W	673 W
Max Operational Junction Temperature	150 °C	200 °C

Table 3.1 Specifications of the investigated devices.

3.2 Test Protocol and Experimental Setup

Each device was initially characterized in its pristine state from both the electrical and thermomechanical perspective, by monitoring the following parameters:

- $R_{ds(on)}$, i.e. the resistance that the channel opposes to the current flow during the transistor ON state;
- Mechanical strain caused by temperature variations during current flow.

After the initial characterization, the devices are subjected to controlled aging cycles periodically interrupted by measurement sessions, in order to evaluate variations in the parameters selected as “sentinel” indicators. Both the characterization and aging conditions are defined based on the datasheet provided by the company and are customized for each technology, allowing to simulate as closely as possible the aging process under real operating conditions.

3.2.1 Power Supply and Driving Circuit

All tests are performed under short-circuit conditions, according to the following circuit configuration.

Figure 3.3 Schematic of the circuit used to carry out the tests.

The driving signal is generated by a National Instruments multifunction board, which produces TTL (Transistor-Transistor Logic) pulses ranging from 0 to 5 V, with frequency and duty cycle adjustable via a management software implemented in Visual Basic.

Figure 3.4 a) National Instruments multifunction board installed inside the PC; b) connector block for managing the board's input/output signals; c) screenshot of the home-made software for signal management.

The signal generated by the NI board follows the TTL standard and so it is insufficient to fully turn on the devices. Before reaching the gate of the device under test (DUT in Figure 3.3), the signal is properly amplified by a driver which allows the required voltage to be reached, while simultaneously isolating the device circuit from the board. This isolation is crucial as it protects the board and the computer if a catastrophic DUT event occurs, which could introduce destructive voltages into the driving circuit.

Figure 3.5 a) Amplification driver for the gate-source signal; b) driver's internal design; c) circuit scheme.

During the transistor OFF time, a power supply charges the capacitance C_1 , consisting of a bank of parallel-connected capacitors with an equivalent capacitance in the order of 100 mF . When the gate signal reaches V_{th} , the device turns ON and the current resulting from capacitors discharge flows through the DUT. The short-circuit condition is achieved by connecting the drain and source terminals to the positive and negative terminals of the capacitors bank, respectively. An additional capacitance C_2 , connected between the drain and source of the DUT, consists of a capacitor characterized by a small capacitance but high operating voltage and low residual inductance. Its function is to absorb the voltage

overshoot that occurs during the switch-OFF, caused by the parasitic inductance of the connecting wires and the high $\frac{di}{dt}$.

During all tests and aging sessions, the values of V_{gs} and I_{ds} are continuously monitored using an oscilloscope. The current is measured using a current probe directly clamped onto one of the cables connecting C_1 to the DUT; for this study we choose to keep the probe always on the positive cable, connected to the drain.

Figure 3.6 a) Oscilloscope used to monitor the values of gate voltage and drain-source current; b) current probe that allows to display on the oscilloscope a voltage signal proportional to the drain-source current.

Since the voltage required to polarize the gate differs between the two types of investigated devices, we realized two analogous experimental setups, one dedicated exclusively to GaN devices and the other to SiC devices. The following table summarized the specifications of the instruments used for each setup and their respective configurations.

DUT	GAN HEMT	SIC MOSFET
National Instruments board	PCIe 6351	PCIe 6353
V_{gs} after driver amplification	7V	17V
Power supply	Nice-Power YTSH R-SPS3030	Electronic Measurements Inc. TCR 20T500-4-D-OV
C_1 Capacitance	150 mF	120 mF
C_2 Capacitance	1.1 μ F	0.1 μ F
Current probe	MICSIG CP2100 AC/DC	Tektronix A621 AC

Table 3.2 Specifics of the two experimental setups.

3.2.2 Electrical Characterization

The electrical characterization consists of a simultaneous measurement of V_{ds} and I_{ds} values over time, from which $R_{ds(on)}$ is directly calculated using Ohm's law:

$$R [\Omega] = \frac{V [V]}{I [A]}.$$

The same NI board that defines the transistor ON and OFF time is also used to acquire the V_{ds} signal and a voltage signal proportional to I_{ds} , ensuring temporal correspondence between all channels thanks to its internal clock. The current probes dynamically convert current into voltage according to a conversion factor that depends on the probe and the selected range of measurement. Once the conversion factor of the instrument is known, the corresponding current in amperes can be determined. For both current probes used, the conversion factor is $10mV/A$.

Measurements are performed in differential configuration: 4 analog-input terminals of the board, two dedicated to V_{ds} and two to I_{ds} , record the positive and negative contributions of each signal, whose difference provides the actual measured value.

The signal applied to the gate determines a ON time of $10 ms$, followed by $1990 ms$ of interdiction, allowing the DUT to recover from the stress induced by the current pulse and to dissipate the generated heat. This condition is achieved by setting in the management software a signal with frequency of $0.5 Hz$ and 0.5% duty cycle. Data acquisition is programmed to start $8 ms$ before the gate signal is applied, allowing to record the entire OFF-ON transient, in addition to the ON period.

The evolution of I_{ds} over time follows the typical capacitor discharge profile. For all characterizations, we choose to keep the peak current value constant by adjusting V_{ds} as needed. Specifically, the values are $60 A$ for the GaN HEMTs and $200 A$ for the SiC MOSFETs.

The following graphs show the time evolution of V_{ds} and I_{ds} for each device class, as well as the corresponding $R_{ds(on)}$ calculated as the ratio between the measured values. The data presented refer to the pristine state of the specified device.

Figure 3.7 On the left side: V_{ds} (black line) and I_{ds} (red line) measured at the ends of the transistors during the characterization phase, consisting in a single 10 ms electrical pulse. On the right side: $R_{ds(on)}$ evolution during the pulse, calculated from the data shown in the left side graphs.

3.2.3 Optical Measurements

Both the circuit configuration and the electrical pulse are the same used for the electrical measurements, allowing to assess the correlation between electrical and mechanical behaviour.

Figure 3.8 shows the experimental setup for the recordings, including details of some components designed and fabricated in the laboratory to complete the experiment.

Figure 3.8 a) Experimental setup for video acquisition; b) illumination system; c) sample holder with adjustable tilt.

The acquisition system consists of an Optronics CR450X3 camera equipped with an optical system to adjust the zoom. The instrument is controlled via the proprietary software Time Bench v2.5. From the configuration menu, recording was set to start via an external trigger on the rising edge of an additional TTL signal generated by the NI board and synchronized with the device switch-ON. Acquisitions are configured with a 10% pre-trigger, allowing to record a temporal segment before the switch-ON, the entire pulse duration, the switch-OFF and the subsequent thermal relaxation. Each video consists of 1112 frames recorded at 10000 fps with a resolution of 160x100 pixels (the only format allowing this acquisition rate) and an exposure time of 1/10000 s.

Considering the limited number of pixels used for video acquisition and the need to capture the entire device, the optical setup required a zoom that reduces magnification, increasing the field of view. The overall lens system magnification is 0.2x, sufficient to project the image of the entire device onto the camera's active area consisting of 160x100 pixels. Furthermore, due to the short exposure time, the images were inherently dark, so a dedicated illumination system was implemented (Figure 3.8 (b)), consisting of a

continuously emitting white LED mounted on a brass support, which in turn is attached to an adjustable *theta-phi* mount. The high brightness of the LED source ensures adequate image quality even under the challenging conditions imposed by the high acquisition speed.

Another home-made component is the sample holder used to secure the devices and keep them stable during recording (Figure 3.8 (c)). It consists of two aluminium plates, one rigidly fixed to the workbench and the other serving as a support plane for the transistor. The plates are connected via three adjustable screw and two high stiffness springs, creating an inclined plane adaptable to different requirements. This configuration was specifically chosen to allow the observation of deformation along the z-axis, projecting its component onto the image plane.

The recorded videos are subsequently processed using MATLAB scripts based on Motion Magnification algorithms, to reveal micrometric deformations of the DUT, and Motion Estimation algorithms, to quantify their magnitude. Both approaches are phase-based, meaning that they evaluate phase variations corresponding to movement.

3.2.4 Controlled Aging Sessions

Following the characterization phase, the DUTs are subjected to a specific aging protocol: since it is not feasible to wait for real operational lifetimes in order to observe degradation phenomena, we defined a condition that simulates realistic operation within the SOA specified by the manufacturer, while still being stressful enough to induce accelerated aging in the device.

The developed protocol requires to connect the transistor under short-circuit condition using the same circuit configuration employed during the characterization phase (Figure 3.3) but now subjecting it to continuous switching at a frequency of 10 kHz , in order to induce repeated thermal and electrical stress events. It is important to note that, although the electrical configuration remains the same, the circuit dynamics are different: during these high frequency switching cycles, the power supply directly provides the energy required to establish the desired current, while the capacitor bank C_1 remains inactive, as it does not have enough time to charge and discharge appreciably. In other words, in this configuration C_1 behaves as a passive component, with no considerable influence on the circuit operation.

To prevent unwanted overheating and maintain a stable temperature, the DUT is mounted on a liquid-cooling system.

Figure 3.9 a) Liquid-cooling system; b) configuration of a GaN HEMT mounted on the cooling system during the aging session.

Throughout the entire process, the V_{gs} at the driver output and the I_{ds} at the transistor's ends are monitored using an oscilloscope, in order to verify the correct execution of the stress cycle and promptly identify any anomalies.

The timing and electrical parameters used during the aging phase differ depending on DUT technology, reflecting the different physical properties of the materials. For GaN HEMTs, each switching session lasts 30 minutes with a peak current value of 20 A; for SiC MOSFETs, each session lasts 90 minutes and the maximum current reaches 65 A.

Figure 3.10 shows the evolution of I_{ds} and V_{ds} during stress phase. The plots display a single switch cycle, in which the DUT is brought into conduction at time $t = 0$ and the current rises to its maximum value within $50 \mu s$, before extinguishing when the gate signal is brought below the conduction threshold. This transient is representative of the cyclic behaviour that repeats throughout the entire duration of the session.

Figure 3.10 V_{ds} and I_{ds} across the transistors during a switching event of the controlled aging phase.

Chapter 4

Data Analysis and Experimental Results

This chapter presents the results obtained by processing the videos recorded during the characterization phases.

A first qualitative analysis employs Motion Magnification algorithms to amplify the motions present in the video. A further processing step analyses the phase variations between consecutive frames in order to quantify the displacements within the image plane. Since the main experimental interest concerns the motion occurring out of the plane, a geometric model was developed to retrieve the actual value of the deformation along the z-axis, assuming that the motion predominantly occurs in that direction. This reconstruction is essential because it enables a direct comparison with independent measurements obtained using a vibrometer, allowing a quantitative validation of the technique.

Part of the computational tools used are based on freely available libraries implemented in MATLAB, released by the MIT CASIL research group through a public repository under an open-source license for research purposes. These codes were used as a solid starting point for the development of the software dedicated to the analysis.

4.1 Qualitative Analysis

Each video was initially processed using a phase-based Motion Magnification software implemented in MATLAB, allowing to visualize the micrometric deformations affecting the devices. The algorithm used is the “*phase amplify*”, available in the MIT repository. The processing parameters were empirically determined after a careful analysis of the images, considering both the limitations imposed by the experimental setup on the signal-to-noise ratio and physical considerations regarding the nature of the phenomena under investigation. The selected parameters are reported in Table 4.1 and discussed below.

PARAMETERS	GAN	SIC
Spatial filter	Half Octave	Half Octave
Temporal filter	FIR Window BP	FIR Window BP
Passband	1-50 Hz	20-50 Hz
Magnification factor	50	70

Table 4.1 Parameters for video processing.

Images are spatially decomposed through Complex Steerable Pyramid, for which the octave step can be adjusted. Decreasing the octave step corresponds to a finer decomposition which, in principle, allows improved spatial resolution but also amplifies the noise contribution. For this reason, a half-octave was adopted, as it represents the best compromise between the maximum achievable spatial resolution and noise management.

The temporal filter is a band-pass (BP) with finite impulse response (FIR), meaning that it responds to an event only for a limited time interval. The choice of the appropriate filter is crucial to preserve the temporal structure of the signal, and FIR filters are the only ones that can be designed to maintain the temporal coherence of events. In contrast, IIR filters (infinite impulse response) are faster but exhibit a strong temporal ringing, producing a lingering echo of the motion even after the actual event has ended.

The passband was selected by exploring ranges of low frequencies, which are typically associated with thermomechanical phenomena. Starting from a wider frequency range, the filtering window was progressively refined by excluding ranges that did not show significant

contributions in the processed videos, until the relevant bands for the analysis were identified.

Finally, the magnification factors were gradually increased until deformations became clearly visible without introducing excessive distortion. The two different values reflect the different magnitude of deformation observed in the two types of devices.

Figure 4.1 shows a comparison of selected frames extracted from the original videos and the corresponding frames from the magnified videos.

Figure 4.1 Frames extracted from the original and magnified videos of a GaN HEMT (top) and a SiC MOSFET (bottom) together with a colour map to emphasize the differences. The selected frames represent the initial condition, before the current pulse, and the moment of maximum deformation. The colour maps highlight intensity variations with opposite signs.

This comparison confirms the effectiveness of the technique: in the original sequences no visually appreciable differences are observed, while in the processed videos the magnification process makes the deformations visible. The colour maps are used to emphasize the pixel-to-pixel differences between the images; the two different colours represent variations of opposite sign and should not be interpreted quantitatively.

Moreover, the observed variations are neither random nor ascribable to algorithm-induced distortions, as they appear consistently with the timing of the electrical pulse and essentially return to zero once the excitation ends, as shown in the representative sequence in Figure 4.2. The colour coding has the same meaning in all presented figures.

Figure 4.2 Frames extracted from the original and processed videos of a GaN HEMT. The first row shows three frames from the original video captured before the current pulse, during the excitation, and after the complete dissipation of the generated heat; the second row reports the corresponding frames after applying the magnification algorithm; the third row displays the difference maps between each original frame and its magnified counterpart.

The use of MM algorithms allows to transform raw video into a powerful diagnostic tool, through which it is possible to identify the areas of the device most affected by thermomechanical phenomena. In the magnified videos, the regions experiencing the highest deformation clearly emerge, providing a first qualitative indication of the areas under greatest stress and potential concern.

4.2 Quantitative Analysis

Videos processed through MM can also provide quantitative information about the magnitude of the deformations. To this end, a further processing step applies a *Motion Estimation* algorithm that extracts the displacement fields. The algorithm works by analysing the temporal evolution of the phase associated with the pyramid's coefficients and computes local motions from phase variations. The displacements in the image plane are obtained by the following relations

$$\Delta x_{img} = \frac{\Delta \varphi_x}{k_x}, \quad \Delta y_{img} = \frac{\Delta \varphi_y}{k_y}$$

where $\Delta \varphi_x$ and $\Delta \varphi_y$ are phase variations along the horizontal and vertical directions of the images and k_x and k_y are the corresponding wavenumbers of the filters used for spatial decomposition.

The values of Δx_{img} and Δy_{img} are calculated for each pixel and frame of the video. Among these data, the displacement corresponding to specific points of interest, identified through the qualitative analysis, were selected. The displacements obtained in this way are measured in pixels and must therefore be converted to μm according to the following relation

$$\Delta L_{img} [\mu m] = \Delta L_{img} [px] \times 14 \left[\frac{\mu m}{px} \right] \times \frac{1}{0.2} \times \frac{1}{\alpha}$$

where:

- $\Delta L_{img} [\mu m]$ is the calculated value in μm
- $\Delta L_{img} [px]$ is the measured value in pixels
- $14 \left[\frac{\mu m}{px} \right]$ is the physical pixel size on the sensor
- $\frac{1}{0.2}$ accounts for the optical magnification of the lens system employed for recording
- α is the magnification factor set in MM algorithm.

4.2.1 3D Reconstruction

The video analysis provides a two-dimensional motion field described by the components x_{img} and y_{img} , which do not represent the actual DUT deformation but rather its projection onto the camera plane. The experimental choice to tilt the DUT with respect to the optical axis introduces a coupling between the motion observed in the image and the real out-of-plane motion, allowing the latter to be determined through geometrical considerations.

Figure 4.3 presents a schematic of the acquisition system, where (x, y, z) denotes the reference frame of the sample and (x_c, y_c, z_c) denotes the camera reference frame.

Figure 4.3 Schematic of the acquisition system geometry, highlighting the DUT reference frame (orange dashed line) and the camera reference frame (solid blue line).

The DUT is tilted by a known angle θ with respect to the optical axis through a rotation around the x -axis. Therefore, the transformation between the two reference frames is described by the rotation matrix

$$R_x(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos\theta & -\sin\theta \\ 0 & \sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{pmatrix}.$$

The coordinates in the camera reference frames are:

$$\begin{aligned}x_c &= x; \\y_c &= y \cos\theta - z \sin\theta; \\z_c &= y \sin\theta + z \cos\theta.\end{aligned}$$

Assuming an orthographic projection, which is justified by the fact that displacements are small compared to the distance between the camera and the DUT, the coordinate measured in the image plane coincides with y_c , i.e.:

$$y_{img} = y \cos\theta - z \sin\theta.$$

This is the general expression relating the real displacement components to the quantity observed in the video. In our specific case, the motion is assumed to occur exclusively along the z direction, with no contribution along y, an assumption consistent with the constraints imposed by the device packaging. Setting $y = 0$, the previous relation reduces to

$$y_{img} = -z \sin\theta$$

and isolating the component of interest

$$z = -\frac{y_{img}}{\sin\theta}.$$

For each processed video, the measured value Δy_{img} was extracted and then used to calculate the actual out-of-plane deformation. This reconstruction is essential to validate the quantitative data, since the values obtained using this geometric model were compared with standard vibrometer measurements, an instrument that (in our configuration) measures displacement exclusively along the z-axis.

4.3 GaN HEMTs Results

This section presents the results obtained for the investigated GaN devices. The out-of-plane deformation over time was analysed for several points selected on the device surface. The general observed trend is a rapid deformation upon the arrival of the electrical excitation, reaching a maximum peak and followed by a relaxation phase. The central region of the DUT is subjected to more pronounced thermomechanical deformations both in magnitude and duration. Small oscillations are also observed in the tail of the signal, likely caused by undesired environmental vibrations.

Figure 4.4 Out-of-plane (z) deformation versus time for a GaN HEMT at several points selected on the DUT surface. The inset shows an optical image of the DUT with the measurement points highlighted; the colour of each point corresponds to the colour used to represent its deformation curve.

The analysis was extended to different aging stages and, to assess the accuracy of the results, the data were compared with laser vibrometer measurements performed at the same aging stage and, approximately, at the same point on the surface. The following figures show comparative plots of the results obtained through the two techniques, together with images highlighting the points where analyses were performed.

GaN 594 MCycles

Point of analysis - Vibrometer

Point of analysis - Motion

GaN 684 MCycles

Point of analysis - Vibrometer

Point of analysis - Motion

Point of analysis - Vibrometer

Point of analysis - Motion

Point of analysis - Vibrometer

Point of analysis - Motion

Figure 4.5 Comparative analysis after the aging sessions. Plots represent the DUT deformations after a total stress time of 16 hours (light blue), 19 hours (blue), 20 hours (green) and 32 hours (yellow); vibrometer data are everywhere reported in red. On the right side of each plot: top, a picture of DUT surface with the point of vibrometric measurement marked in red; bottom, the first frame of MM video at the corresponding age, with the point of analysis marked in the same colour of the solid line in the plot.

From a quantitative perspective, a systematic overestimation of the deformation amplitude is observed in the data obtained from video analysis. To simplify the comparison, Table 4.2 reports the maximum values measured with the two techniques and the corresponding percentage difference between them.

N x 10⁶ Cycles	MOTION	VIBROMETER	DEVIATION
594	6.10 μm	6.03 μm	1.16%
684	7.05 μm	6.93 μm	1.73%
720	5.76 μm	5.58 μm	3.22%
1152	5.82 μm	5.60 μm	3.92%

Table 4.2 Comparison of the maximum deformation amplitude measured with the two techniques.

The observed differences can be attributed to the procedure used to reconstruct the motion along the z-axis, in which any contribution regarding the in-plane motion was neglected, introducing a systematic bias that led to the overestimation. It is worth noting, however, that the percentage deviation between the measurements increases with DUT aging, suggesting a change in the deformation pattern: the stress induced by the power cycling sessions caused structural degradation that altered the deformation dynamics, making the lateral component increasingly significant. This resulted in a larger error in the reconstruction of the out-of-plane deformation, but it is a highly relevant finding as it provides new insights for the study and interpretation of thermomechanical phenomena in this class of devices, information that could not have been obtained from vibrometer measurements alone. Another difference concerns the relaxation dynamics: in the video data, a faster relaxation with return to the initial condition is observed, while the vibrometer measurements show a slower descent that exponentially tends to zero but does not fully return within the measurement time. This discrepancy can be traced back to the baseline removal process, as well as the previously mentioned environmental vibrations, both of which contributed to altering the tail of the signal.

Overall, the consistency in the shape of the rising curves and the temporal synchronization of the events confirms the validity of the optical technique as a tool for measuring deformations. Looking ahead, an improvement to the experimental setup would involve the introduction of a second camera recording from a different angle, allowing the motion components to be separated and analysed individually. Further analysis will also be necessary to identify and eliminate the external source of vibrations responsible for the noise in the signal tail.

4.4 SiC MOSFETs Results

This section discusses the analysis of SiC devices. The videos recorded during the characterization phases were processed following the same steps used for the GaN devices, ultimately reconstructing the out-of-plane deformation to perform the comparison with the vibrometer measurements. However, unlike the GaN devices, the SiC signals were more strongly affected by environmental vibrations. In fact, the deformations in SiC devices are significantly smaller than those observed in the GaN HEMTs and, in order to make the phenomenon visible, high magnification factors had to be used, which amplified not only the signal of interest but also the parasitic vibrations present in the experimental setup.

The presence of these vibrations had already been observed during the analysis of GaN devices, where they were negligible compared to the measured deformation amplitude; in this case, in contrast, they become comparable to the signal and the resulting curves appear strongly perturbed, with oscillations superimposed on the DUT thermomechanical response.

Figure 4.6 Deformation over time for SiC devices. Each plot shows the attempted reconstruction of the out-of-plane motion for the point marked in the images above. The contribution of external vibrations is comparable to the magnitude of the phenomenon under investigation, making quantitative analysis unreliable.

It is worth noting that these oscillations are on the micrometre scale and were not detectable prior to video processing. Their presence only emerged after applying the MM

algorithms, at a stage when repeating the acquisitions was no longer possible. In this case, a quantitative comparison would therefore be meaningless, as it is not possible to separate the true DUT response from the external vibrations.

At this moment, it is planned to repeat the measurement campaign on the SiC devices, once the necessary modifications to the experimental system have been implemented. Strategies to improve the setup are currently underway, such as adopting a stiffer and damped mechanical base for DUT mounting to reduce the transmission of vibrations from the surrounding environment and from the connecting wires. Additionally, using a more modern power supply could significantly contribute to reduce the observed oscillations. These improvements will allow for better sensitivity and repeatability of the measurements in the future and will enable the effective extension of the technique to SiC MOSFETs as well.

Conclusions

The work presented opens the possibility of integrating Motion Magnification techniques as a fast and effective method to study the dynamics of deformations in power devices. A full understanding of these processes is indeed essential to improve reliability and device lifetime.

Optical measurements alone do not allow direct visualization of the deformations, as their magnitude is on the micrometre scale and therefore below the sensitivity of any conventional optical system. However, thanks to the application of Motion Magnification, it is possible to detect and investigate these phenomena.

The results obtained on GaN devices demonstrated the ability not only to visualize the deformations but also to describe their dynamics, showing good quantitative agreement in comparison with reference measurements. New details also emerged regarding the effects of thermomechanical fatigue: the induced stress caused changes in the deformation geometry, introducing an in-plane deformation component that becomes increasingly significant with aging.

For the SiC MOSFETs, experimental limitations currently allowed only a qualitative analysis, which however made it possible to identify the regions most affected by the deformation, providing indications of areas of higher stress and potential criticality.

There remains room for improvement in the experimental setup, with the goal of making the system fully reliable as a research tool.

This work is supported by the R-PODID project, which is funded by the Chips Joint Undertaking and its members, including the top-up funding by the National Authorities of Italy, Turkey, Portugal, The Netherlands, Czech Republic, Latvia, Greece, and Romania under grant agreement No. 101112338.

References

- [1] A. Kumar *et al.*, “Wide Band Gap Devices and Their Application in Power Electronics,” *Energies (Basel)*., vol. 15, no. 23, p. 9172, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15239172.
- [2] E. O. Prado, P. C. Bolsi, H. C. Sartori, and J. R. Pinheiro, “An Overview about Si, Superjunction, SiC and GaN Power MOSFET Technologies in Power Electronics Applications,” *Energies (Basel)*., vol. 15, no. 14, p. 5244, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15145244.
- [3] J. Millán, P. Godignon, X. Perpiñà, A. Pérez-Tomás, and J. Rebollo, “A Survey of Wide Bandgap Power Semiconductor Devices,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 2155–2163, May 2014, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2013.2268900.
- [4] T. Kimoto and J. A. Cooper, *Fundamentals of Silicon Carbide Technology*. Wiley, 2014. doi: 10.1002/9781118313534.
- [5] O. Slobodyan *et al.*, “Analysis of the dependence of critical electric field on semiconductor bandgap,” *J. Mater. Res.*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 849–865, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1557/s43578-021-00465-2.
- [6] B. J. Baliga, “Power semiconductor device figure of merit for high-frequency applications,” *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 455–457, Oct. 1989, doi: 10.1109/55.43098.
- [7] X. She, A. Q. Huang, O. Lucia, and B. Ozpineci, “Review of Silicon Carbide Power Devices and Their Applications,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 10, pp. 8193–8205, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2017.2652401.
- [8] E. A. Jones, F. F. Wang, and D. Costinett, “Review of Commercial GaN Power Devices and GaN-Based Converter Design Challenges,” *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Top. Power Electron.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 707–719, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2016.2582685.
- [9] T. P. Chow, “Wide bandgap semiconductor power devices for energy efficient systems,” in *2015 IEEE 3rd Workshop on Wide Bandgap Power Devices and Applications (WiPDA)*, IEEE, Nov. 2015, pp. 402–405. doi: 10.1109/WiPDA.2015.7369328.
- [10] M. Buffolo *et al.*, “Review and Outlook on GaN and SiC Power Devices: Industrial State-of-the-Art, Applications, and Perspectives,” *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 1344–1355, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TED.2023.3346369.

- [11] J. Lutz, H. Schlangenotto, U. Scheuermann, and R. De Doncker, *Semiconductor Power Devices*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2011. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-11125-9.
- [12] Shaoyong Yang, A. Bryant, P. Mawby, Dawei Xiang, Li Ran, and P. Tavner, "An Industry-Based Survey of Reliability in Power Electronic Converters," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 1441–1451, May 2011, doi: 10.1109/TIA.2011.2124436.
- [13] S. M. I. Rahman *et al.*, "Emerging Trends and Challenges in Thermal Management of Power Electronic Converters: A State of the Art Review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 50633–50672, 2024, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3385429.
- [14] M. Ciappa, "Selected failure mechanisms of modern power modules," *Microelectronics Reliability*, vol. 42, no. 4–5, pp. 653–667, Apr. 2002, doi: 10.1016/S0026-2714(02)00042-2.
- [15] M. d'Ambrosio *et al.*, "Investigation into the Aging Mechanisms of a SiC-Based Power MOSFET by Thermal and Thermomechanical Analysis," in *2025 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Automotive (MetroAutomotive)*, IEEE, Jun. 2025, pp. 168–172. doi: 10.1109/MetroAutomotive64646.2025.11119275.
- [16] J. G. Chen, N. Wadhwa, Y. J. Cha, F. Durand, W. T. Freeman, and O. Buyukozturk, "Modal identification of simple structures with high-speed video using motion magnification," *J. Sound Vib.*, vol. 345, pp. 58–71, Jun. 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2015.01.024>.
- [17] K. Hong, G. Liu, W. Chen, and S. Hong, "Classification of the emotional stress and physical stress using signal magnification and canonical correlation analysis," *Pattern Recognit.*, vol. 77, pp. 140–149, May 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patcog.2017.12.013>.
- [18] A. Davis *et al.*, "Visual Vibrometry: Estimating Material Properties from Small Motions in Video," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 732–745, Apr. 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2016.2622271>.
- [19] C. Liu, A. Torralba, W. T. Freeman, F. Durand, and E. H. Adelson, "Motion Magnification," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 24, no. 3, Jul. 2005, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1073204.1073223>.
- [20] H.-Y. Wu, M. Rubinstein, E. Shih, J. Guttag, F. Durand, and W. Freeman, "Eulerian Video Magnification for Revealing Subtle Changes in the World," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 31, no. 4, Jul. 2012, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2185520.2185561>.

- [21] N. Wadhwa, M. Rubinstein, F. Durand, and W. T. Freeman, "Phase-based video motion processing," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 32, no. 4, Jul. 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2461912.2461966>.
- [22] N. Wadhwa, M. Rubinstein, F. Durand, and W. T. Freeman, "Riesz pyramids for fast phase-based video magnification," in *IEEE International Conference on Computational Photography*, Santa Clara, California, USA, Jun. 2014. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCPHOT.2014.6831820>.
- [23] T. H. Oh *et al.*, "Learning-based Video Motion Magnification," in *European Conference on Computer Vision*, Munich, Germany: Springer, Oct. 2018, pp. 633–648. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-01225-0_39.
- [24] D. Fortun, P. Bouthemy, and C. Kervrann, "Optical flow modeling and computation: A survey," *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, vol. 134, May 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cviu.2015.02.008>.
- [25] B. D. Lucas and T. Kanade, "An iterative image registration technique with an application to stereo vision," in *DARPA Imaging Understanding Workshop*, Vancouver, 1981, pp. 121–130.
- [26] B. K. P. Horn and B. G. Schunck, "Determining optical flow," *Artif. Intell.*, vol. 17, pp. 185–203, Aug. 1981, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-3702\(81\)90024-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-3702(81)90024-2).
- [27] "Pyramid (image processing)," Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. Online Available: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pyramid_\(image_processing\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pyramid_(image_processing))
- [28] J. Portilla and E. P. Simoncelli, "A Parametric Texture Model Based on Joint Statistics of Complex Wavelet Coefficients," *Int. J. Comput. Vis.*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 49–70, Oct. 2000, doi: 10.1023/A:1026553619983.
- [29] I. Berrios, "An Introduction to Steerable Pyramid Decompositions," Medium: human stories & ideas. Online Available: <https://medium.com/@itberrios6/steerable-pyramids-6bfd4d23c10d>
- [30] P. Burt and E. Adelson, "The Laplacian Pyramid as a Compact Image Code," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 532–540, Apr. 1983, doi: 10.1109/TCOM.1983.1095851.
- [31] W. T. Freeman and E. H. Adelson, "The design and use of steerable filters," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 13, no. 9, pp. 891–906, 1991, doi: 10.1109/34.93808.

- [32] I. Berrios, “Complex Steerable Pyramids: How to Decompose the Local Phase of an image,” Medium: human stories & ideas. Online Available: <https://medium.com/@itberrios6/complex-steerable-pyramids-3cf7b99ff9fc>
- [33] P. Kovési, “Phase Congruency Detects Corners and Edges,” in *VIIIth Digital Image Computing: Techniques and Applications*, Sydney, Australia: CSIRO Publishing, Dec. 2003.
- [34] D. J. Fleet and A. D. Jepson, “Computation of component image velocity from local phase information,” *Int. J. Comput. Vis.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 77–104, Aug. 1990, doi: 10.1007/BF00056772.
- [35] T. Gautama and M. A. Van Hulle, “A phase-based approach to the estimation of the optical flow field using spatial filtering,” *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1127–1136, Sep. 2002, doi: 10.1109/TNN.2002.1031944.
- [36] E. P. Simoncelli, W. T. Freeman, E. H. Adelson, and D. J. Heeger, “Shiftable multiscale transforms,” *IEEE Trans. Inf. Theory*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 587–607, Mar. 1992, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/18.119725>.
- [37] N. Wadhwa *et al.*, “Motion microscopy for visualizing and quantifying small motions,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 114, no. 44, pp. 11639–11644, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1703715114.
- [38] D. J. Fleet, *Measurement of Image Velocity*. Boston, MA: Springer US, 1992. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4615-3648-2.